

ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION IN CROSS-BORDER MATTERS – A SOCIO-LEGAL
OVERVIEW FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF POLISH LAWYERS

Alternative forms of dispute resolution (ADR) are increasingly used to resolve conflicts effectively. Among lawyers, they are also growing in popularity. More and more conflicted parties try to solve their problems outside the courtroom. Negotiation, mediation and arbitration are now an integral part of dispute resolution throughout Europe. Especially in large commercial disputes, ADR is used frequently and effectively. The most developed Western European companies negotiate or participate in mediation and arbitration before entering into litigation. In some countries, like the Netherlands, it is estimated that over 90% of business disputes are resolved amicably (Anon 2019b:20–23; Nordic Council of Ministers 2002:27–49).

In the age of globalisation, informal ways of resolving disputes are particularly gaining in value. With rising international trade and population migration, the number of cross-border disputes, both business and consumer, is growing. In the case of consumers, the numbers and relevance of disputes in family matters and cross-border consumer matters are particularly increasing (Hodges 2012:195–97; Hodges, Benöhr, and Creutzfeldt 2012; Lipiec 2022:15–31). When a case involves individuals and companies operating in different countries, living in different jurisdictions and speaking different languages, it is extremely difficult to resolve conflicts in the traditional judicial manner. Choosing a single body to resolve a dispute for participants from many parts of the world can prove to be a breakneck undertaking. Moreover, in the classic method of conflict resolution, the dispute involves lawyers, judges and prosecutors who are attached to a particular country, legal system and culture and are not interested in operating in many legal spaces. Additional difficulties for the classic judicial resolution of conflicts are procedural issues, such as court jurisdiction, summonses for hearings and service of correspondence. Hence, the judicial process involving many international factors becomes complex and lengthy. Therefore, in relatively small cases of international (cross-border) nature, there are no court proceedings. Often, the parties prefer to abandon the case rather than undertake the expense and difficulty of conducting complicated procedures; ADR methods can be particularly helpful in this type of case (Anon 2021a; Gaultier 2013:42–56).

The popularity of ADR in international relations varies by country, legal environment and types of cases. In Poland, negotiation, mediation and arbitration are widely known among advocates, legal advisers and judges. Similarly, they are increasingly popular among managers of large companies. There is a broad community of mediators and arbiters. There are also numerous specialised institutions in Poland that conduct arbitration, including international

arbitration. Individuals are completely unfamiliar with these forms of dispute resolution and avoid using them. Despite the existence in Poland of satisfactory legal conditions for conducting ADR and quite common knowledge of professionals, in practice, out-of-court forms of conflict resolution are not used. Even in family matters, where mediation is legally preferred, the number of cases referred to mediation is very low. Especially in the area of conflict resolution with international elements, mediation in Poland is a niche practice. In cross-border cases of individuals, ADR are practically not used and in business disputes they remain a curiosity in Poland (Biel and Jopek-Bosiacka 2016:149–61; Gmurzyńska and Morek 2012:20.01-20.75; Rudolf et al. 2016:12–44).

Polish advocates and legal advisers are the professional group that has a particularly good perspective on the use of ADR in practice in Poland. Therefore, we asked Polish jurists to talk about the practical use of ADR in Poland in cases with foreign elements. We asked whether foreigners staying in Poland, foreign companies in Poland and Poles working abroad participate in forms of alternative conflict resolution. Furthermore, we asked Polish lawyers to indicate how mediation, arbitration and negotiation with foreign participation are conducted. In addition, we raised the issue of the actual functioning of Polish mediators and arbitrators in cases involving foreigners or foreign companies and the activity of non-Polish forms of mediation or arbitration involving Poles.

Preliminary discussions with Polish jurists allowed for the formulation of the main hypothesis: **The use of alternative dispute resolution methods in international relations is rare in Poland and its number and relevance is practically not increasing.** It was also noted that ADR with international elements other than commercial does not occur in Poland. Additionally, the methods of out-of-court dispute resolution in cross-border relations indicated in Polish and EU legal acts concerning family and consumer cases do not really function in Poland. Finally, the disputants do not have the knowledge and willingness to participate in arbitration-mediation procedures in cross-border cases despite their attorneys' or judges' knowledge of ADR procedures.

The main objective of the study is to explain the mechanisms, reasons and effects of ADR methods in cross-border, international relations and with international elements (explication objective). The implementation objective of making proposals to remedy the lack of use of ADR to resolve cross-border disputes also remains important. The descriptive objectives concerning mediation or arbitration remain less relevant here.

RESEARCH METHODS

The survey results are part of a larger study of the Polish justice system and the provision of legal services by Polish lawyers (Lipiec 2020). The survey was conducted between 7 October 2017 and 22 January 2019, and then completed between November 2020 and March 2021.

The entire study was based on a variety of quantitative and qualitative research methods. The methodological core was based on in-depth structured interviews with representatives of bar associations from all over Poland. In addition, the obtained results were checked, supplemented, and verified by means of non-reactive material research, the primary method of which was website content analysis and other statistical materials. Legal acts and acts of law application were analysed within the functional method of analysis (Babbie 2008:342–60; Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias 2001; Kędzierski 2018:34–46).

The currently presented results of the study on alternative dispute resolution in international and transnational matters were obtained mainly through the method of in-depth structured interviews (SSI). Interviews were conducted with 43 members of councils of advocates' and legal advisers' bar associations from all over Poland (*okręgowa rada adwokacka, ORA; okręgowa izba radców prawnych, OIRP*). The distribution of interviewees was even across the country. One council was represented by one interviewee. Interviews were conducted in person usually at the headquarters of the bar councils; they were then recorded, transcribed, coded, categorised, and translated into English. Due to the uniformity of the legal advisor profession and the advocate profession, the analysis of the interviews was done jointly, as both professions are treated identically in the report. The Atlas.ti program was used to work with the research material. The analysis of the interviews was focused on relevance. The conducted research has a strictly qualitative character (Anon 2021b; Horton, Macve, and Struyven 2004; Nicpoń and Marzęcki 2010:246–51; Przybyłowska 1978:62–64).

The study belongs to the paradigm of sociology of law and legal anthropology. Therefore, the research works of Richard Abel and Adam Podgórecki were the model to follow. However, the general assumptions of the study were based on the achievements of grounded theory as interpreted by Kathy Charmaz. Important here is the conclusion that the content of the research should be grounded in its course, and the researcher must listen completely to the testimony of the interviewees and not impose his or her opinions and findings. The main guide for conducting the interviews was Steiner Kvale's methodological recommendations, especially for conducting qualitative interviews (Abel 1985; Charmaz 2013; Kvale 2012; Podgórecki and Kurczewski 1971).

RESEARCH RESULTS

Globally, the development of ADR has long been prominent. As the phenomenon of globalisation increases, the number of international (cross-border) cases resolved by negotiation, mediation and arbitration similarly increases. We are witnesses of the institutional development of ADR. According to *International Arbitration Information* by Aceris Law LLC globally, we have currently more than 200 permanent mediation or arbitration panels working internationally (Anon 2020b). The number of smaller permanent arbitration and mediation forums is more than ten times larger, while the number of ad hoc initiatives is vast and difficult to determine. However, despite the existence of many permanent and temporary out-of-court dispute resolution initiatives, most of them provide a commercial service. Still, mediation and arbitration for individuals are not very popular (De Boisseson 1999:349–55; Stürner, Gascón Inchausti, and Caponi 2015).

Parallel to the development of organisations, a legal structure of international and cross-border ADR is developing. The expansion of legal institutions for mediation and arbitration is embracing an intrastate, legal-international and corporate character. All these three regimes complement and interpenetrate each other. Particularly noteworthy here are EU regulations that facilitate the conduct of cross-border mediation and arbitration in EU countries in civil and commercial matters (especially the 2008 Directive and 2013 Directive) (Anon 2008, Anon 2013f, Anon 2013). Recommendations of the Council of Europe on family mediation also play an important role in conducting cross-border family mediation (Anon 2021i). Moreover, national Polish regulations in each field of law are progressively facilitating the conduct of international mediation and recognition of arbitration court judgments (Anon 2021a, Anon 2021j; Van Dyck et al. 2011:52–85; Zemke-Górecka, Mendrek, and Rogula 2021:27–51).

Meanwhile, the number of active mediators is growing every year. This phenomenon concerns all European countries, although it is particularly visible in Poland. There are currently 26 mediators' associations in Poland, but the number of all active mediators is unknown. According to the Ministry of Justice, the number of mediations conducted by order of the court or mediation agreements approved by the Polish courts is regularly escalating annually by 10% (Anon 2021k). The number of out-of-court mediations is unknown, but there is a belief that it is increasing mainly in the area of family mediations. A similar situation exists in the case of arbitration conducted in Poland. Here, it is estimated that the number of procedures is growing year on year by 20%. However, this form of dispute resolution almost entirely concerns the resolution of business and commercial problems. No mediation or arbitration statistics indicate the exact number of cases involving international elements, although they do report that the

numbers of such cases are rising (Anon 2020c; Gójska 2013:100–126; Nowaczyk 2009:145–49).

Polish advocates and legal advisers are potentially well prepared to participate in ADR. Currently, academic education and legal applications include content on arbitration mediation (Anon 2018, Anon 2019a). Therefore, some of jurists also act as mediators and arbitrators. The mediation centres of the Polish Bar Council (*Naczelna Rada Adwokacka, (NRA)* and the National Chamber of Legal Advisers (*Krajowa Izba Radców Prawnych, (KIRP)*) are among the most numerous in the country (Anon 2021d, Anon n.d.). Most Polish jurists are familiar with ADR procedures and have at least basic information on mediation, negotiation and arbitration. While, however, it is a fact that for the Majority of Polish legal professionals, information on out-of-court settlement methods is purely theoretical and basic. Relatively few of them are active mediators and arbitrators. Only 31 out of 750 advocates and legal advisers operating in the mediation centres of the NRA and the KIRP declare themselves as mediators or arbitrators capable of handling international cases, and only 165 speak at least one foreign language. For most Polish legal professionals, ADR is still a curiosity. Only a minority actively participate in these procedures as party representatives, arbitrators or mediators (Gotshal 2014).

Polish lawyers highlight that despite the increasing involvement of legal professionals in ADR and effective changes in the ADR market and legal developments, mediation, arbitration and negotiation remain a niche topic. Especially in cross-border (international cases), these methods are vaguely used in the practice of most Polish jurists. Indeed, excepting a small group of international legal specialists, Poles do not use supranational ADR. This applies both to private mediation and negotiation as well as to mediation commissioned by the courts. Theoretical knowledge of lawyers and an accessible legal and institutional environment do not translate into an actual increase in the number of mediations and arbitrations in international cases. Only in disputes between large multinational corporations do occasional opportunities for negotiation or arbitration arise. In some types of disputes or companies they are the standard. In the case of smaller Polish companies and individuals, however, lawyers do not really see much need or willingness for mediation or negotiation in international relations. If such cases do appear, they are not very visible (Bogucki 2018:20–25).

Yet, despite the relative increase in the number of cases of mediation, arbitration and negotiation in international relations, it is still less popular in Poland than in Western countries, especially the United States. Furthermore, the high level of competence of lawyers and more numerous mediation and arbitration initiatives do not translate into the number and importance of conducted out-of-court forms of dispute resolution. Still, Polish jurists and their clients do

not trust conciliatory forms of agreement. In Poland, a brutal court decision is more important than a mutually beneficial agreement; hence, the still low popularity of ADR and the increasing burdening of courts with often trivial problems. This situation is characteristic of Poland and Eastern European countries. In other regions of the world, the popularity of mediation and arbitration is growing rapidly and translates into the number and importance of cases (Alexander, Walsh, and Svatos 2017; Townsley 2016). An experienced legal advisor and arbitrator from Gdansk, Poland, notes:

I remember even 10 or 15 years ago when I was interested in matters of out-of-court dispute resolution. In fact, I teach trainee legal advisers about these matters. When we look at other countries, we really notice that we are at the tail end of the world. If you look at the statistics, it turns out that there are countries where only 10% of cases end up in court or even less. For example, in the Netherlands, but also in the United States, it is only 4% of cases. Everything is resolved out of court. Sometimes through lengthy negotiations, but there are also agreements in huge cases. An example from the Twinning Meeting, where we had a seminar on mediation. The English came to us and they played the mediation meeting very beautifully and showed us how to solve the case. But the problem in Poland is that everybody, for example the judges, think that lawyers are reluctant to mediate, that they are bothered by mediation. This is the general perception of the role of attorneys in mediation. And then, you get a little reluctant. You do not want to encourage parties to mediate or to participate in arbitration procedures. Mediation and arbitration can also be a bit complicated, because you need to have a lot of soft skills, and in the courtroom, as we know, there is usually not much going on. I also agree that mediation is very valuable and important. Unfortunately, ADR do not work in Poland.

Polish jurists also note that at the turn of the 21st century there was a great enthusiasm in Poland for international arbitration, negotiation and mediation. Perhaps this was the result of a lack of confidence in the Polish judiciary and the intensive penetration of the young Polish economy by American companies. At that time, the first Mayor arbitration initiatives such as the Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Commerce (*Sąd Arbitrażowy przy Krakowej Izbie Gospodarczej (KIG)*) developed (Anon 2021q). However, the first decades of the 21st century witnessed a regression of international ADR in Poland, similarly related to the lack of

legal environment. Only recently have out-of-court forms of dispute resolution been gaining in importance. A very experienced legal advisor from Katowice describes this situation thus:

In the second half of the 1990s it seemed that arbitration was a panacea for everything, but it turned out (especially for those foreign entities that were dissatisfied) that it took a very long time, and then you still had to have the arbitral award approved by the court, which made the proceedings even longer. Therefore, there was a period of boom, when we had a lot of these arbitration cases involving domestic and foreign entities. The lengthening of the proceedings meant that there were fewer and fewer.

There is a small group of advocates and legal advisers in Poland and a few professional Warsaw-based mediators who are engaged almost exclusively in conducting international (cross-border) business negotiations or arbitrations. These professionals are almost solely involved with large multinational corporations based in Warsaw. For lawyers in general, this is still an exotic topic – few have participated in such initiatives. According to the survey participants outside Warsaw, non-corporate lawyers may very rarely encounter only subcontracting elements of arbitration cases or negotiations. This is usually in connection with analysing contractual provisions regarding arbitration clauses. Yet, these are isolated situations that do not require the participation of a lawyer in the actual arbitration or negotiation. It can be assumed that, in Poland, there are several lawyers who have personally participated in international arbitration as a party representative or arbitrator.

Representatives of this small group of experienced professionals emphasise that they are generally not enthusiastic about participating in arbitration or mediation. ADR has still not completely been adopted in Poland. Despite great interest, knowledge and legal environment, clients and their attorneys are still distrustful of mediation or arbitration. They complain about the Polish justice system, especially about the lengthiness of proceedings and the complexity of procedures, but they prefer to participate in clearly codified and proprietary procedures rather than fancy mediation or arbitration. Therefore, few Polish jurists recommend their clients to participate in such procedures. The exceptions here are English, Japanese or American companies, which as a rule demand negotiations and other forms of dispute resolution. This is due to their legal tradition.

However, if a client wishes a lawyer to pursue out-of-court dispute resolution, Polish professionals usually do not recommend mediation or arbitration in Poland. Jurists believe that

in Poland there is still a strong temptation for unfair, biased dispute resolution. Therefore, they usually suggest settling disputes in foreign arbitrations in Vienna, Stockholm, Paris or Switzerland and even in some cases in Moscow. In Poland, only the Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Commerce (*KIG*) is regarded as fulfilling the highest global standards. Legal advisors from Szczecin and Gdansk, who participate in mediations and arbitrations as attorneys for the parties, mediators and arbitrators, indicate that

These are provisions for large contracts. In the case of smaller matters, no one thinks about arbitration. If I give my opinion on a contract and there is a clause in it for international arbitration, I immediately give a negative opinion on such a provision, because it is consenting to something uncertain and we do not know what rules of procedure it is based on. As a matter of principle, I do not agree with arbitration courts at all, even in the Polish legal system, because if there is mediation or arbitration, I do not really believe in it. But this is my conviction as an attorney. I prefer the worst judgment, but in a common court, because the rules of procedure are well established there, whereas with arbitration many different situations occur.

Polish lawyers involved in mediation and arbitration in international matters highly value the Polish Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Commerce. Many of the interviewees are or have previously been arbitrators there. According to most of them, it is the only highly specialised arbitration court in Poland that is competent to handle any dispute, including cross-border and international ones. Polish jurists trust the tribunal and its arbitrators. They point to the organisation as meeting all national and international arbitration standards, as do similar institutions in Paris, Stockholm and Lausanne (Anon 2020b). The specialists who comprise the team of arbitrators are the best in Poland and also experts in international matters. As indicated by the court, the team includes 200 arbitrators. Significantly, of the 192 arbitrators registered with the court, as many as 45 have a nationality other than Polish, while all Polish arbitrators speak at least one foreign language. Ninety-six arbitrators indicate international arbitration as their specialisation. Out of 160 arbitration cases conducted by the Court of Arbitration, 30 per year are international or cross-border in character. A similar level of professionalism and international orientation is displayed by the court's mediators (Anon 2017, Anon 2021i, Anon 2021c; Kurier365 2019t). However, a significant problem of this court and mediation platform is concentration on large commercial arbitration and internet domain related cases. Other cases, mainly consumer ones, are generally not conducted here.

Polish legal experts report that there are very many international and cross-border mediation initiatives and several arbitration forums in Poland. Nevertheless, none of them obtains such a position in international cases as the KIG (Anon 2021b, Anon 2021h; Ultima Ratio 2019). In other arbitration courts, cases with international elements appear very rarely. If they do, they concern medium-sized companies with a regional scope. Research participants emphasise that they have encountered single arbitration cases with international elements in the arbitration court at the Lewiatan Confederation (*Konfederacja Lewiatan*) (Anon 2021p). Here, the cases also relate exclusively to commercial matters. The Lewiatan Confederation does not have as much experience and reputation as the court at KIG, but year by year its importance in Polish international commercial arbitration is increasing. This is certainly influenced by the relatively large number of foreign arbitrators among 209 arbitrators, 30 are foreigners and all of them speak at least one foreign language. In addition, the selected arbitrators specialise in different aspects of international commercial matters (Anon 2021c). It seems that this arbitration forum will be a kind of competition for the KIG. It is only a pity that here arbitration is conducted solely in economic matters. The Toruń legal adviser describes the most important Polish arbitration courts thus:

Clients often ask about arbitration in Paris. In Polish courts, Lewiatan often appears, the National Chamber of Commerce, and the arbitration court at the Chamber. But especially there is no preference that it has to be this or that, and different proposals are made in this field.

Additionally, the legal professionals emphasise that mediation-arbitration cases in the international context in other arbitral tribunals do arise. However, these cases are very rare. Over the period of their long careers, they have noticed single cases of a transnational nature in the Arbitration Court of Chambers and Economic Organisations of Greater Poland (*Sąd Arbitrażowy Izby i Organizacji Gospodarczych Wielkopolski*) and in the Arbitration Court for Domains at the Polish Chamber of Information Technology and Telecommunications (*Sąd Polubowny ds. Domen przy Polskiej Izbie Informatyki i Telekomunikacji*) (Anon 2021o, Anon 2021r). These two organisations also deal almost exclusively with commercial cases. Pomeranian lawyers emphasise that in Gdynia there is the International Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Shipping (*Międzynarodowy Sąd Arbitrażowy przy Krajowej Izbie Morskiej*) for maritime economy (Anon 2021m). Its arbitrators mostly specialise in international disputes. Yet, probably due to its high level of specialisation, location in Gdynia and its small size, it is

not well-known and completely unrecognised outside of Pomerania. Moreover, the scope of international cases is limited to maritime matters. Nevertheless, this arbitration court should be noted as potentially the most international in Poland. One of the arbitrators describes the functioning of the court thus:

There is also the International Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Shipping in Gdynia. And it has strictly international arbitration cases, but there are not many cases there either. For example, we had a case recently between a Russian entrepreneur and a Polish entrepreneur. And then Russian lawyers represented the Russians. There were suspicions that the Polish arbitration court was not objective because of bias against the Russians. That is not true, but that is how it works. However, there are sometimes maritime cases from European Union countries. They are rare but they do occur. Polish, European and non-European cases are similar. International cases are most often ad hoc arbitrations.

However, the number and relevance of cases with international elements is unknown here. The number of mediations with international elements is also unknown. Certainly, international commercial arbitration cases arouse more interest among Polish lawyers than similar mediations.

Polish still have very limited confidence in mediation and arbitration. Even Anglo-Saxon companies that traditionally negotiate, mediate and arbitrate extensively are wary of Polish arbitration initiatives. When contracts are drawn up between Polish and foreign companies, in which arbitration clauses are expected, provisions for Polish arbitration are rare (Gmurzyńska 2008:30–38; Sobczak 2017:171–74). This equally applies to the most prestigious Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Commerce. Foreign entrepreneurs are much more likely to submit their disputes to arbitrators of the ICC International Court of Arbitration in Paris, LCIA International Court of Arbitration in London, Arbitration Institute of the Stockholm Chamber of Commerce, Zurich Chamber of Commerce, Vienna International Arbitral Centre and even the ICAC International Court of Arbitration in Moscow (Anon 2020u, Anon 2020y, Anon 2021g, Anon 2021v, Anon 2021w, Anon 2021x). These arbitration courts also have Polish arbitrators, albeit in very limited numbers. Still, these platforms enjoy greater recognition, trust and impartiality than Polish arbitration courts. In practice, the use of these arbitrations by contractual parties is extremely rare. Clauses for these courts usually remain dead and apply only to the most serious contracts.

Unfortunately, all proposals to submit problems to the arbitration process still concern the largest business transactions. Participation in arbitration, or particularly mediation of an international nature by individuals in non-business matters, tends to be completely absent. Attorneys from Gdansk and Poznan note foreign, international arbitration issues:

I am sometimes involved in drafting contracts with foreign contractors. When we negotiate a dispute resolution clause, everyone would prefer to submit to the jurisdiction of either a Polish court, as far as Poles are concerned, or a Polish arbitration. That is why a neutral one is chosen, such as in Stockholm, Vienna or Switzerland – Zurich, Bern or Lausanne. These are the most common directions. Actually, Vienna, Stockholm and London are the most common. It is customary that these are chambers with extensive experience, and cases are most willingly submitted to arbitration there. And besides, they seem more neutral to the parties, especially Austria and Sweden.

Foreign elements appear in international arbitration. There is a certain group of arbitrators who deal with such things. For example, they are members of the Court of Arbitration at the International Chamber of Commerce in Paris. These are people who know the language very well; they are excellent lawyers. In Poland, there are also foreign elements, such as the need to conduct an arbitration case in a foreign language, as agreed by the parties. Of course, the arbitrator must know the language in which the case is being conducted. Arbitration is a court of law, so if someone wants to resolve a case amicably, they usually settle it through negotiations without arbitration. Only in the case of really big, serious cases, mainly international ones, is arbitration organised, but only when it is absolutely impossible to reach an agreement.

All forms of negotiation, mediation and arbitration in international matters relate to commercial matters. The interviewees never met individuals who would postulate or participate in ADR in the context of international affairs. Besides, for individuals, mediation or negotiation in ordinary everyday matters is also an abstraction. Lawyers emphasise that they would rather not recommend consumers to participate in mediation or proceedings before conciliation courts, although appropriate procedures and organisations do exist in Poland. According to experts, a judgment by a common court is always better than an uncertain mediation settlement and

arbitration court judgment for a consumer. However, this view is slowly being devalued in favour of younger lawyers becoming more involved in out-of-court forms of dispute resolution.

Despite lawyers' reserve towards ADR, they note that, especially in cross-border family matters, international mediation should gain in importance. Such solutions are strongly supported by the European Union (EU) and the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE). There are also relevant legal regulations. Jurists emphasise that in situations where parents and children are located in different countries it is difficult to conduct cross-border litigation. The ideal solution here is international mediation in family matters, which can now be conducted online or by correspondence. Attorneys specialising in family matters point out that especially cross-border family mediation conducted remotely may also soon develop very rapidly in Poland. Examples of EU and Western European solutions prove the great potential and need in this area (Mania 2015:76–86; Miranda 2014:97–125, 165–261; Zagórska 2013:104–15).

In addition, the lawyers participating in the survey note a rise in problems related to population migrations, cross-border shopping and other consumer contracts in cross-border relations, such as travel services. Consequently, the number of civil and cross-border disputes before the European courts is increasing. However, the problem of this classical form of conflict resolution is the far-reaching procedural difficulties linked to the cross-border nature of the process (e.g. service, summonses, translations) and cultural differences in legal and language knowledge. Thus, consumers are very reluctant to enter into cross-border litigation. Lawyers therefore see the prospect of solving civil cross-border consumer disputes precisely in the form of ADR. A large field for the development of these forms of conflict resolution is small consumer disputes in the field of tourist services and cross-border trade. Lawyers predict that within the next five years, the 'market' for cross-border consumer mediation and arbitration in Europe will develop so that 75% of disputes in mail order and tourism will be resolved outside of the ordinary courts (cf Hodges et al. 2012; Van Dyck et al. 2011).

Legal professionals have noted interesting initiatives by the European Commission to resolve cross-border consumer disputes. The Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) and SOLVIT initiatives are highly appreciated by them, but are considered to be only the first proposals in this area. Lawyers regard them as a step in the right direction, but not a sufficient one. They emphasise that they are very little known and are not trusted by consumers in Poland. Poles still choose to refer cases to common courts or accept defeat rather than use these EU dispute resolution initiatives. Despite appreciating these solutions, the survey participants do not identify these ADR platforms as important media for their clients to resolve their conflicts with

traders (Anon 2020a:1–4; Ciechomska 2006:18–22; European Commission 2021n, 2021s, 2021; Handley 2018; Mania 2010:15–21).

ADR initiatives in the international context do not address administrative, criminal, labour law issues. These potential fields of out-of-court dispute resolution remain beyond the mental outlook of Polish lawyers and their clients. The fact is that even cases from these branches of law can be solved by ADR and equally in international (cross-border) cases. So far, such activities are not observed in Poland. Despite the growth and deepening of mediation and arbitration initiatives, the view of the primacy of court judgments over the always victorious, cheaper ADR solutions still prevails in Poland. In everyday and local matters, Poles and their attorneys rarely resort to mediation or arbitration; hence, in more complicated and less understandable international matters, these forms of conflict resolution are not gaining popularity. It is apparent that this situation is slowly changing. It will take some time before international arbitration or mediation becomes as popular in Poland as it is in Western Europe (Kocur et al. 2016:4–31; Rudolf et al. 2016:12–72).

CONCLUSIONS

Alternative ways of resolving conflicts are growing in popularity each year. In some Western European countries, Japan and the United States, mediation, arbitration and negotiation are the main forms of communication between parties with different views. ADR is particularly developing in international business cases involving large companies. The huge number of mediators and arbitrators and mediation-arbitration institutions means that the development of this form of conflict resolution in the Western world is slowly beginning to replace litigation. And, in areas such as family and consumer matters, these forms of procedure are developing intensively. Thanks to mediation or international arbitration, borders are blurring, which cease to be barriers to conciliatory problem solving (De Boisseson 1999:350–256; Townsley 2016:242–49; Van Dyck et al. 2011:84–91).

In Poland we can also observe intensive development of out-of-court forms of conflict resolution. Especially commercial mediation is gaining importance. However, mediations in cross-border and international cases are still very rare in Poland, and, in fact, are not conducted. There are several important arbitration forums in Poland, especially the Arbitration Court at the Polish Chamber of Commerce. They handle cases mainly in the field of commercial arbitration. This field of work is developing year by year, but much more slowly than in other Western European countries. International cases appear in Polish arbitration courts, but rarely. They usually concern very large contracts and disputes between large companies. Unfortunately,

Polish entrepreneurs still have little confidence in Polish arbitrators and mediators. Thus, they choose to refer their disputes to arbitration in Paris, Stockholm or Switzerland rather than in Warsaw. Nevertheless, arbitration clauses or actual arbitrations in cross-border or international cases remain sporadic in Poland.

The research hypotheses posed in the introduction are fully confirmed. In Poland, the functioning of ADR in cross-border and international matters is practically non-existent, at most of a marginal character. Any such mediation or arbitration concerns only business cases. Even though Polish law and EU law create a legal environment and promote the functioning of cross-border consumer or family mediation, it does not practically function in Poland. The parties' attorneys, the courts and the parties do not even know that in cross-border family or consumer disputes they can use cross-border mediation or arbitration. The problem here is the high level of mistrust among legal professionals, gaps in their knowledge and lack of confidence in the non-state dispute resolution system. Not without significance is also the lack of proper upbringing in Poland promoting peaceful problem solving instead of confrontation. Furthermore, Poland's limited legal trade with foreign countries means that there is less need to resolve cross-border disputes than in highly interconnected countries.

Alternative forms of conflict resolution are much more valuable than judicial forms. Hence, their development in Poland in cross-border and international perspectives should be seen as an important objective for the whole justice system. The change in the current state of affairs must begin in schools. Students must be taught peaceful, consensual conflict resolution. School curricula should be supplemented with elements of mediation and school negotiation. And, in the course of legal education, more emphasis should be placed on the practical training of future lawyers in ADR. Moreover, it is vital to promote mediation or arbitration among ordinary citizens and legal professionals. It is possible that, in cross-border disputes, parties in conflict should be obliged to use mediation and arbitration before going to court. This would relieve the courts of the burden of handling difficult and bureaucratic disputes with international elements (Barabas 2018:11–29; Czyżowska 2018:197–203; Żaczkiewicz-Zborska 2021).

Changes to the law on international ADR are less important here as the current law in this area is satisfactory. What is most important now is the practical promotion and use of forms of ADR in consumer, family and other civil international matters. Legal compulsion of parties to alternative proceedings should be considered as a kind of pre-judgment before cases are referred to ordinary proceedings. The solution to the lack of ADR in international cases is very simple. At the same time, it is extremely difficult.

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